

Incidence of ragged stunt in floating rice in Thailand

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Severe outbreaks of ragged stunt virus disease (RSV) occurred in floating rice in the Central Plains of Thailand in 1981. Infected plants showed the disease symptoms typically associated with paddy rice—dark green and ragged leaves, spirally twisted leaves, severe stunting (see figure) with occasional bunched growth from an upper node, and incomplete panicle emergence with unfilled grains. Infection was widespread in the deepwater rice areas, particularly in Nakhon Nayok Province.

Symptoms appeared in August shortly after flood inundation. In 38

fields examined from November 1981 to January 1982, more than 7% of the stems showed RSV symptoms. Infected plants labeled in the field in October and November at the end of the vegetative phase were totally unproductive at maturity 2 months later. Six severely infected farmers' fields (averaging 23% infected stems) had a mean yield of 1.4 t/ha, 16 slightly infected fields (averaging 5% infected stems) had a mean yield of 2.5 t/ha.

Disease incidence did not appear to be related to high populations of the ragged stunt vector, the brown plant-hopper *Nilaparvata lugens*. ■

Severe stunting of Pin Gaew 56 caused by natural infection of ragged stunt virus. October 1981, Ayutthaya, Thailand. Water depth was 92 cm.

Rice varietal ability to withstand prolonged darkness in screening for submergence tolerance

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Because light penetration is low at water depths of 110 cm, the exceptional survival of FR13A in 110-cm water could be related to ability to withstand prolonged periods of low light intensity. Fifty-day-old seedlings of susceptible (KDML105), moderately tolerant (IR8234-OT-9-2), and tolerant (FR 13A) entries were subjected to total darkness, without submergence, for 10 days. Also, leaf yellowing was measured on 30-, 40-, and 50-day-old seedlings after 4, 6, and 10 days of darkness.

Response to total darkness for 10 days was similar to reaction to submergence in the standard screening test (Table 1). Tiller number was also reduced. Older plants were slower to exhibit leaf yellowing (Table 2). After 10 days of darkness, 50-day-old seedlings of moderately tolerant IR8234-OT-9-2 had

Table 1. Comparative response of rice genotypes^a to submergence and darkness, Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Thailand 1982.

Genotype	Survival (%) after 7 days		Tillers (no./pot)		
	Dark treatment 10 days	Submerged 10 days	Dark treatment 10 days	Submerged 10 days	Control
KDML105 (susceptible)	0.0	10.0	0.0	3.0	33.0
IR8234-OT-9-2 (moderately tolerant)	50.0	35.0	21.0	15.0	43.0
FR13A (tolerant)	73.0	61.0	30.0	25.0	41.0

^a 50-day-old seedlings.

Table 2. Leaf yellowing symptoms of susceptible, moderately tolerant, and tolerant rices in darkness, Huntra Rice Experiment Station, Thailand, 1982.

Variety or line	Plant age (days)	Leaf yellowing (%) of plants at indicated days of darkness		
		4d	6d	10 d
KDML105 (susceptible)	30	90.0	100.0	100.0
	40	15.0	95.0	100.0
	50	0.0	50.0	95.0
IR8234-OT-9-2 (moderately tolerant)	30	15.0	90.0	100.0
	40	5.0	60.0	90.0
	50	0.0	5.0 ^a	20.0
FR13A (tolerant)	30	15.0	80.0	95.0
	40	5.0	50.0	80.0
	50	0.0	5.0 ^b	5.0

^a Leaf tip only. ^b Leaf margins only.

4 times as much leaf yellowing as highly tolerant FR13A.

If a strong association between leaf yellowing and survival under darkness

exists, large-scale screening for submergence tolerance could be conducted without deep ponds and water pumping costs. ■